

Effect of Sediment Load on Bed Morphology of a Movable-bed Symmetrical Confluence

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Abstract

River confluences are locations where two or more rivers merge and continue to flow as a single stream. At a confluence, hydrodynamics, sediment transport processes, and morpho-dynamics influence and modify each other. The flow structure of the confluence zone interacts with the sediment transport, which results in bed morphology changes. In this study, two experiments were carried out in the large-scale open channel confluence of İzmir Kâtip Çelebi University Hydraulics Laboratory, where two symmetrical tributaries forming a right-angle lead to a main channel. While the flow rate from each tributary was equal and 20 l/s for both experiments, the sediment loads were set as 0 kg/min in both tributaries in one experiment and 0.1 kg/min in both tributaries in the other one. The flow depth at the downstream of the confluence was adjusted to be 5.0 cm on top of a 20.0 cm deep sand layer on the bed. The bed topography and the water surface were measured at the end of the experiments ($t = 15$ h) by using the distance measurement feature of a Vectrino probe and three ULS-40D probes, respectively. The results of the experiment where sand was supplied to the tributaries essentially confirmed the morphological model of mobile bed confluences reported in the literature as applying to asymmetrical confluences (including two tributary mouth bars, two bank-attached bars, one central scour hole and one mid main-channel bar), whereas the clear-water experiment only complied with some results of a limited number of previous equivalent studies

Keywords: open channel confluence, sediment transport, morphological structure, sediment load

Introduction

Confluences are locations where two or more open-channels with equal or different water and sediment discharge rates merge and continue to flow downstream as a single channel. Confluences are rather common[features in natural rivers and systems of artificial open-channels [1].

River confluences can display symmetrical or asymmetrical planforms, depending on the angle between the two converging channels and their orientation in relation to the downstream channel (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. (a) Asymmetrical, (b) Symmetrical River confluence

At a river confluence, hydrodynamics and sediment transport processes influence and modify each other. The interplay between the hydrodynamics of the confluence zone and the patterns of sediment transport results in changes of the bed morphology [2] and vice-versa. Because of these intricate changes, confluences pose risks associated with flooding, bank erosion, navigation, structural safety of bridges or other nearby structures [3], among others. Thus, river confluences are of great importance for some scientific disciplines and engineering works. It is well established that confluence hydraulics

and bed dynamics are rather complex as they depend on a large number of parameters. Among these parameters, the junction angle, the planform, and the converging water discharge and sediment transport rates, are usually the most important.

In his pioneering research work, Taylor [4] studied the hydrodynamics of confluent rigid-bed open channels and obtained basic information that keeps its pertinency at present. Also, Webber and Greated [5] worked on hydrodynamics using one-dimensional approach. Since the 1980s, a large number of studies have been carried out on the hydro-morpho-dynamics of mobile-bed open channel junctions, including experiments in laboratory channels and field studies.

The first comprehensive laboratory study on the bed morphology of mobile-bed confluences was performed by Mosley [6], who used a small-scale experimental set-up both with symmetrical and asymmetrical planforms. He covered different discharge ratios (ratios of converging water discharges), junction angles, and amounts of sediment supply, and observed the occurrence of a scour hole in the confluence zone of both types of planforms. He also concluded that the scour hole depth decreased as the total sediment load (of both upstream channels) increased.

Best [7] investigated the sediment transport phenomenon at asymmetrical confluences both in the laboratory and in nature. In the laboratory, he has imposed five different junction angles (15° , 45° , 70° , 90° and 105°) and concluded that no scour hole formed for 15° , whereas an increasingly deeper scour hole developed as the junction angle increased. Best [7] was also the first author who suggested a morphological model of mobile bed open channel confluences.

At present, the morphological model of natural symmetrical and asymmetrical mobile-bed confluences, established on the basis of both laboratory and field works (see Figure 2), is known to include all or most of the following bed features: sediment accumulation zone (underneath a flow stagnation zone) at the vertex of the junction; two tributary mouth bars or a main channel bar and a tributary mouth bar (depending on the type of planform); a scour hole (in most cases); one or two bank attached bars (also depending on the type of planform); and a downstream mid channel bar (in some cases).

Figure 2. Bed morphology at open-channel confluences, (a) Symmetrical, (b) Asymmetrical

The experimental and field measurements done by Ashmore and Parker [8] for a braided river show that the confluence angle is the most important parameter regarding the dimensions of the scour hole. An increase in total water discharge, confluence angle (between 30 degrees and 90 degrees) or grain size can increase the scour depth too.

Rhoads [9] concluded that the occurrence of a scour hole would inevitably lead to sediment accumulation, the mid channel bar, downstream from the maximum velocity zone due to the decrease flow velocities and the reduction of turbulence intensities as the shear layer disappears.

Recently, Guillén-Ludena [10] investigated, among other topics, the effect of the channel width ratio (ratio between the main channel width and the width of the tributary channel) on the morpho-dynamics of asymmetrical mobile bed confluences. His experiments were performed under live bed flow conditions, with continuous sediment supply to both channels. The increase of the width ratio induced the increase of the size of the bank-attached bar due to the increase of the size of the recirculation zone developing downstream of the downstream junction corner. Bombar and Cardoso [1] and Balouchi et al. [11] investigated the effects of bed load transport rates on the morpho-dynamics of asymmetrical confluences. Both studies concluded that the deepest scour hole was formed under clear-water flow conditions, i.e., with no sediment feeding. Zhang et al. [12] investigated the bed morphology of a natural

asymmetrical confluence characterized by a discordant bed, low sediment load in the tributary, high sediment load in the main channel, and very large momentum flux differences between the two converging channels. According to their data, no significant bank-attached bar was observed because of the lack of flow separation. According to Bombar and Cardoso [1], the depth of the scour hole decreased with sediment load in the tributary. Shakibaeinia et al. [13] used a 3D numerical model to simulate sediment transport and bed morphology in laboratory-scale and field confluences across a wide range of confluence angles and discharge ratios. They found that the decrease of the confluence angle and the increase of the discharge ratio, the size of the scour hole can decrease, and its location can move further downstream in the main channel. Yu et al. [14] conducted laboratory experiments in a confluence flume under movable bed conditions until initial bed equilibrium was reached. Then, they fixed the bed and introduced colored fine sediment to the tributary to simulate contaminated sediment. The study examined how junction angle and discharge ratio affect the morpho-dynamics and the deposition patterns. Their results indicated that the junction angle primarily influences the confluence bed morphology and sediment transport, while discharge ratio is a secondary factor.

From the above, it can be concluded that, with the exception of the small-scale experiments of Mosley [6], all the mentioned laboratory studies were performed for asymmetrical confluences. This also applies to the large majority of other research works (mostly, field studies) that can be found in the literature. So, the present study, whose preliminary results are presented herein, was conceived to identify the effect of sediment load on the bed morphology of a large-scale laboratory mobile-bed symmetrical confluence, in the attempt to contribute to close the existing knowledge gap.

Experimental Study

Experimental Set-up

Two experiments were carried out in the Hydraulic Laboratory of İzmir Kâtip Çelebi University: the first one, hereafter Experiment 1, under clear water flow conditions (with no sediment supply); the second one, Experiment 2, under live bed flow conditions (with sediment supply).

The experimental set-up was a large symmetrical confluence which consisted of two rectangular tributary channels merging into an equally rectangular, wider, downstream main channel (see Figures 3 and 4). Both tributaries were 4.9 m long and 1.00 m wide, whereas the main channel was 6.5 m long and 2.00 m wide, the lateral walls of these channels being 0.90 m high. They were made of smooth concrete, the same as their horizontal bottom. The junction angle between the two tributaries was 90°, and its bisectrix was aligned with the longitudinal axis of the downstream main channel (see Figure 4).

Figure 3. Experimental facility at the laboratory

A 20.0 cm thick layer of uniform sand (median diameter, $d_{50} = 1.044$ mm; geometric standard deviation, $\sigma_g = 1.16$) was added on top of the horizontal concrete bottom. This layer was delimited downstream by a rigid bed sill, this way also creating a 1,50 m long sand trap on top of the concrete bottom. The apparatus still included an equally thick 3.0 m long sand-bed reach, followed by a downstream water chamber whose water level could be regulated through an adjustable tail gate (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Plan view of experimental set-up (all units are in cm)

The experimental set-up included a water reservoir placed underneath the laboratory floor. The water was pumped out from there with the help of two centrifugal pumps and circulated in two independent water circuits (one per pump). Each circuit was connected to a different tributary. The circuit of the right tributary was equipped with an electromagnetic flowmeter used to measure the water discharge (± 0.1 l/s). The discharge of the left tributary was measured through a 0.70 m wide basin weir, equipped with a limnimeter to measure the head of the approach flow (water level in the reservoir relative to the weir crest), h , to the precision of ± 0.1 mm. The discharge coefficient of the weir, C_d , was calculated with the empirical equation of Rehbock [15]:

$$C_d = 0.602 + 0.83h/P \tag{1}$$

where P is the height of weir. The discharge in each circuit was adjusted through one valve per circuit until it reached the predefined value.

The flow depth along the flume, adjusted by operating the tailgate, was measured with a limnimeter (± 0.1 mm) and kept constant during the experiments (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. (a) Adjustable tailgate, (b) Limnimeter

Two conveyor belts (see Figure 6) were used to supply sand to the flow at the upstream cross-section of the tributaries during Experiment 2. Both conveyor belts were 1.0 m long and 0.6 m wide, but moved at different speeds: the left conveyor belt moved at 6.67 cm/min; the right one moved at 1.54 cm/min.

Figure 6. Conveyor belts (a) Right, (b) Left

The bed topography was measured by using the distance measurement feature of a down-looking Vectrino probe (Figure 7.a), whereas the water surface level was measured with a set of three ULS-40D

probes (Figure 7.b) installed on a rigid frame that could be placed at different x positions along the channels. The error margin of bed measurements and water surface measurements were of the order of 1 mm and 0.01 mm, respectively.

Figure 7. a) Down-looking Vectrino, b) ULS-40D probes

Experimental Procedure

Excluding the sediment supply in Experiment 2, both experiments were carried out following the same procedure. First, the 20.0 cm deep sand layer was made perfectly plan with the help of a moving platform. Then, the tailgate was raised and the pumps started pumping a very small discharge rate (2 l/s) into the tributaries to guarantee that the sand bed grains were not entrained. When the flow depth reached 15.0 cm, the discharge rate of both circuits was gradually increased to 20.0 l/s by opening the valves, which also guaranteed that the sand bed was not disturbed. After that, the tailgate was slowly lowered until the flow depth reached 50.0 mm above the sand bed, immediately upstream of the downstream water chamber. This instant was considered as the beginning of the experiments ($t = 0$). The experiments lasted 15:00 h after this instant.

In Experiment 2, 1.5 kg of sand was uniformly distributed every 15 minutes on the left conveyor belt. Similarly, 6.5 kg of sand were distributed every 65 minutes on the right conveyor belt. This way, the sediment supply rate was 0.1 kg/min in both tributaries.

The bed topography was recorded at the end of each experiment ($t = 15$ h). Topography measurements were made at a grid of points 10 cm apart for x and y directions in the main channel, and at 25 cm apart in the tributaries. The water surface was measured just before stopping the experiment ($t = 15$ h). These measurements were made at sets of three points defined 25 cm apart in x-axis along the main channel, at $y = \{-50.0; 0.0; \text{and } 50.0\}$ cm and along the longitudinal axes of the tributaries.

Experimental Results and Discussion

Results of Experiment 1 (clear-water)

The horizontal projection of the main-channel bed morphology at the end of Experiment 1 is given in Figure 8.a, covering the area defined by $0 \text{ m} \leq x \leq 6 \text{ m}$ and $-1 \text{ m} \leq y \leq 1 \text{ m}$. A photo of the plan view of the same area is presented in Figure 8.b.

Erosion was observed near the downstream corners of the tributary mouths expanding symmetrically downstream towards the center of the main channel and forming a sort of scour corridors whose depth decreased along x. These corridors were similar to those observed by Bombar and Cardoso [1] and Balouchi et al. [11] in their clear-water experiments in asymmetrical confluences. Differently, two bank-attached bars formed in the present study between the scour corridors and the adjacent lateral walls of the main channel, confirming these features of the morphological model summarized in Figure 2.a. However, no scour hole was detected starting at the vertex formed by the walls of both tributaries, which is most likely due to the absence of sediment supply into the tributaries. The mid-channel bar was also absent, whereas it is not clear whether tributary mouth bars developed or not.

Figure 8. Bed topography of Experiment 1 at t = 15 h: (a) measurements; (b) photo

To try and clarify if the tributary mouth bars occurred or not, Figure 9 presents the longitudinal bed and water surface profiles measured along the central axes of both tributaries at $t = \{0;0; 15;0\}$ h (beginning and end of the experiment), r being the distance from the tributary mouth along the same axes. Figure 10 displays the same information on the main channel for $y = \{-50.0; 0.0; \text{ and } 50.0\}$ cm; it also indicates the end flow depth at $x = 4.00$ m and $x = 6.00$ m, rendering it clear that this variable decreased downstream. This means that the flow was not exactly uniform due to the fact that the initial mobile bed was horizontal.

Figure 9. Initial and final bed morphology and water surface in both tributaries for Experiment 1 (a) Right, (b) Left

Overall, the bed profiles of the main channel confirmed the scour corridors and the bank attached bars. The z values at $x = 0$ indicate that no clear sand bars were developing at the tributary mouths since $z \approx 20.0$ cm in there. Finally, the presence of a sediment accumulation zone at the vertex of the tributaries' junction ($x = 0.0$; $y = 0.0$) cm (Figure 10.b) seems clear, in accordance with the model of Figure 2.a.

Figure 10. Initial and final longitudinal profiles of the water surface and the bed morphology for Experiment 1 (a) $y = 50.0$ cm, (b) $y = 0.0$ cm, (c) $y = -50.0$ cm

Results of Experiment 2 (live-bed)

The horizontal projection of the main channel bed morphology at the end of Experiment 2 is given in Figure 11.a), covering the area defined by $0 \text{ m} \leq x \leq 6 \text{ m}$ and $-1 \text{ m} \leq y \leq 1 \text{ m}$, whereas a photo of the same area is offered in Figure 11.b).

Overall, the morphology of the bed is much closer to the model depicted in Figure 2.a) than in the case of Experiment 1. Although there is no evidence that equilibrium was reached, there is also no doubt that, adding to the bank attached bars identified in the clear water case (Experiment 1), the central scour hole and a mid-channel bar have developed or were still developing. Since the size of the bank attached bars is larger than on Experiment 1, it can be concluded that the extra accumulated sand came from either the tributaries or the central scour hole, or both.

Figure 11 does not allow any conclusion on the presence of the tributary mouth bars and the sediment accumulation zone. To facilitate the analysis, Figure 12 presents the initial water surface profiles and the bed profiles measured along the central axes of both tributaries at $t = \{0:0; 15:0\}$ h, whereas Figure 13 displays the same information on the main channel for $y = \{-50.0; 0.0; \text{and } 50.0\}$ cm.

Figure 11. Bed topography of Experiment 2 at t = 15 h: (a) measurements; (b) photo

The most noticeable differences between Figures 9 and 12 indicate the development of tributary mouth bars in Experiment 2 as the bed level raised quite significantly in this case at the tributary mouths as compared with Experiment 1. From Figures 10 and 13, it can also be concluded that the bank attached bars were more pronounced than in Experiment 1 and that, differently from the latter a central scour hole starting at the vertex of the tributaries' junction was excavated and a mid-channel bar was created in Experiment 2.

Figure 12. Initial and final bed morphology and water surface in both tributaries for Experiment 2 (a) Right, (b) Left

Figure 13 also shows the absence of the sediment accumulation zone, which can indicate that the equilibrium morphology was not yet reached at t = 15:00 h. The bed morphology was not exactly

symmetrical (Figure 11.a). This lack of symmetry was pointed out by a deeper talweg and a lower bank attached bar downstream of the right tributary ($y = -50.0$ cm), as compared to the left. This asymmetry can be attributed to minor differences (within reasonable experimental errors) of the water and sediment supply to both channels, but they are more likely ascribable to the oscillatory nature of the talweg of movable bed open channels. The asymmetry was facilitated by the large width of the main channel downstream and would probably lead to meandering if the walls of this channel were not rigid and the experiment continued for a longer time. This hypothesis requires further investigation in the future, which can be performed in the same experimental apparatus by eliminating the sand trap so as to create a longer downstream channel.

Figure 13. Initial and final longitudinal profiles of the water surface and the bed morphology for Experiment 2: (a) $y = 50.0$ cm, (b) $y = 0.0$ cm, (c) $y = -50.0$ cm

Conclusions

The present study aims to identify the effect of sediment load on the bed morphology of a large-scale laboratory mobile-bed symmetrical confluence, in the attempt to contribute to close existing knowledge gaps. For this purpose, two experiments were carried out on the open channel confluence in İzmir Kâtip Çelebi University Hydraulics Laboratory, under clear water (Experiment 1) and live bed (Experiment 2) conditions. The influence of the sediment load on the confluence bed morphology can be summarized through the following conclusions:

1. In the presence of sediment supply to the tributaries (Experiment 2), the bed morphology closely resembled the morphological model of natural symmetrical and asymmetrical mobile-bed confluences. It included two tributary mouth bars, two bank attached bars, a slightly asymmetrical central scour hole and a mid-channel bar; contrarily, it did not display the sediment accumulation zone at the vertex of the tributaries' junction.
2. In the absence of sediment supply (Experiment 1), the bed morphology was significantly different from the above morphological model. Although bank attached bars and a sediment accumulation zone were observed, no tributary mouth bars and no mid-bar in the main channel could be identified, whereas, instead of a central scour hole, two scour holes were observed near the downstream corners of the tributary mouths, extending symmetrically downstream towards the center of the main channel and forming two scour corridors, somehow confirming results of

Bombar and Cardoso [1] and Balouchi et al. [11] for clear-water experiments in asymmetrical confluences.

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References

- [1] Bombar G, Cardoso AH. Effect of the sediment discharge on the equilibrium bed morphology of movable bed open-channel confluences. *Geomorphology* 2020; 367.
- [2] Constantinescu G, Miyawaki S, Rhoads B, Sukhodolov A. Numerical analysis of the effect of momentum ratio on the dynamics and sediment-entrainment capacity of coherent flow structures at a stream confluence. *Journal of Geophysical Research* 2012; 117(F4028). doi.org/10.1029/2012JF002452.
- [3] Ghobadian R, Shafai Bajestan M. Investigation of sediment patterns at river confluence. *Journal of Applied Sciences* 2007; 7(10): 1372-1380.
- [4] Taylor EH. Flow characteristics at rectangular open-channel junctions. *American Society of Civil Engineers* 1944; 70: 119–121.
- [5] Webber NB, Greated CA. An investigation of flow behavior at the junction of rectangular channels. *Proceedings of Institute of Civil Engineers* 1966; 34(3): 321–334.
- [6] Mosley MP. An experimental study of channel confluences. *The Journal of Geology* 1976; 84(5): 535–562.
- [7] Best JL. Sediment transport and bed morphology at river channel confluences. *Sedimentology* 1988; 35:481–498.
- [8] Ashmore P, Parker G. Confluence scour in coarse braided streams. *Geography Publications* 1983; 295.
- [9] Rhoads BL, Sukhodolov AN. Spatial and temporal structure of shear-layer turbulence at a stream confluence. *Water Resources Research* 2004; 40: 1–13.
- [10] Guillén-Ludena S. Hydro-morpho-dynamics of open-channel confluences with low discharge ratio and dominant tributary sediment supply (doctoral thesis). Portugal: Instituto Superior Técnico, Da Universidade de Lisboa; 2015.
- [11] Balouchi B, Shafai-Bejestan M, Ruther N, Rahmanshahi M. Experimental investigation of flow pattern over a fully developed bed at a 60° river confluence in large floods. *Acta Geophysica* 2022; 70: 2283-2296.
- [12] Zhang T, Feng M, Chen K. Hydrodynamic characteristics and channel morpho-dynamics at a large asymmetrical confluence with a high sediment-load main channel. *Geomorphology* 2020; 356.
- [13] Shakibaenia A, Zarrati AR, Tabatabai MRM. Three-dimensional numerical study of river channel confluence with bed changes. *Proceeding of 32nd IAHR Congress*; 2007; Venice, Italy. 32(2): 609–617.
- [14] Yu Q, Yuan S, Rennie CD. Experiments on the morpho-dynamics of open channel confluences: implications for the accumulation of contaminated sediments. *JGR Earth Surface* 2020; 125(9).
- [15] Rehbock T, Discussion of precise weir measurements by EW Schoder and KB Turner. *Transactions of the American Society of Civil Engineers* 1929, 93(1):1143–1162.